

Synthesis and Characterization of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Divalent Nickel

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THE coordination tendencies of β -diketo compounds are well established. These ligands are widely used to prepare the new mixed ligand complexes, where they may act as primary or secondary ligand. They often behave as bidentate ligand but sometimes can also act as unidentate ligand e.g., $\text{Me}_2\text{Si}(\text{acac})_2$ ¹. The chemistry of metal β -diketonates is well documented^{2,3}. The present study describes the complexes formed by the interaction of bis(ethylenediamine or propylenediamine) nickel(II) chloride with β -diketone or β -ketoesters and characterized by analytical, magnetic and spectral data.

Experimental

Bis(ethylenediamine) and bis(propylenediamine) nickel(II) chloride were prepared according to method described in the literature⁴. Preparative work was carried out under absolute anhydrous conditions. β -keto compounds were dried by the literature procedures.

Preparation of the complex bis(ethylenediamine) (acetylacetonato) nickel(II) chloride: Bis(ethylenediamine) nickel(II) chloride (0.001 mole) with an excess of acetylacetone in absence of any other solvent, was refluxed till a clear green solution was obtained. On keeping the clear solution overnight a crystalline compound separated out. This was filtered and the adsorbed solvent was removed under reduced pressure at room temperature. The crystalline compound was washed with ethanol-ether mixture and dried *in vacuo*.

Similar methods were used for the preparation of the rest of the complexes.

Physical measurements: The electronic spectra of these complexes were recorded on Carl VSU-2 spectrophotometer using Carl Zeiss alcohol solution. The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} in KBr pellet. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature by using Gouy's method in alcohol solution. Analytical estimations were carried out by the standard methods.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were found soluble in methanol and ethanol. It has been observed that when reactions are carried out under anhydrous condition, the $-\text{NH}_2$ group of diamine does not condense with carbonyl group of β -keto compound. On the other hand, it has been observed in several

cases that the carbonyl group of β -keto compound condensed with $-\text{NH}_2$ group to generate an azomethine group if the reaction is carried out in aqueous media⁵.

The observed and calculated elemental analysis show close resemblance within the experimental limits. The values of the magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) (Table 1) of these complexes are in the range 2.94 B. M. to 3.20 B. M. suggesting the presence of two unpaired electrons; hence the complexes are spin free which most probably have near octahedral stereochemistry.

The observed spectral data and the ligand field parameters are given in Table 1. Three bands have been observed in each complex in the region 570 cm^{-1} to 11050 cm^{-1} , 15870 cm^{-1} to 18020 cm^{-1} and 25510 to 30300 cm^{-1} . The ground state of octahedral d^8 system is A_{2g} and the above spin allowed transitions assuming distorted octahedral geometry of the complexes may be assigned $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(F)$, $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ and $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ in order of increasing energy and labelled as ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 respectively. For d^8 complexes with O_h symmetry, Lever⁶ observed that the configuration interaction between $T_{1g}(P)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ excited states lower the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from the theoretical value 1.8 to 1.5-1.7 which is in conformity with our experimental data supporting the distortion in octahedral geometry. Various numerical fitting methods for d^8 ion suggested by Koning⁷ have been applied. The calculated values are in good agreement with the experimental values. The values of β show a trend of covalent bonding in these complexes. The value of nephelauxetic parameter (h_2) and crystal field parameter (f)⁸ for the ligands used give the comparative estimation of the value of covalence character ($1-\beta$) and the value of Dq in the metal complexes respectively. The spectral parameters $10Dq$, B , Dq/B , β and ν_2/ν_1 are also consistent with the proposed distorted octahedral stereochemistry^{7,9}.

In the mixed ligand complexes of acetylacetone and β -ketoester there will be considerable electron release resulting in the shifting of C—O and C—C bands to higher frequency when additional ligand is bonded to metal ion while the electron drain from the ring system shifts the above bands to lower frequency. Hence it is very difficult to explain precisely the shifting of the band either to higher or lower frequency region. But the definite and marked shifts in the position of the bands from the parent complex show the bonding of the second ligand to metal. This can be seen by comparing the respective modes given in Table 2.

The change in $\nu_{\text{C—C—C}}$ stretching mode due to addition of acetylacetone indicate the change in the angle of C—C—C bond i.e. double bond single bond interaction changes. This indicates that most of the frequency shift in the strained ring carbonyl are due to the changes in the geometry rather than large changes in force constant¹⁰. Perusal of

NOTES

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC DATA, ELECTRONIC BANDS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS (cm⁻¹)

Complex	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	10Dq	B	β	Dq/B	ν_3/ν_1	h_x	f factor
[Ni(en) ₂ (acac)]Cl	2.94	10990	18020	30300	10990	1023	0.97	1.06	1.63	0.25	1.26
[Ni(en) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	3.19	11050	17860	29240	11050	930	0.88	1.18	1.61	1.00	1.27
[Ni(en) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	3.08	10420	16980	28410	10420	942	0.90	1.10	1.63	1.93	1.20
[Ni(pn) ₂ (acac)]Cl	3.20	9670	15870	27550	9570	980	0.93	0.97	1.65	0.58	1.10
[Ni(pn) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	3.01	10530	16180	25510	10530	673	0.64	1.56	1.53	3.00	1.21
[Ni(pn) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	3.10	10100	16000	25970	10100	778	0.74	1.29	1.58	2.17	1.16

TABLE 2—SIGNIFICANT IR BANDS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

[Ni(en) ₂] Cl ₂	[Ni(en) ₂ (acac)]Cl	[Ni(en) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	[Ni(en) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	[Ni(pn)] Cl ₂	[Ni(pn) ₂ (acac)]Cl	[Ni(pn) ₂ (MAA)]Cl	[Ni(pn) ₂ (EAA)]Cl	Assignments
3410w	—	3420s	—	—	3400sh	—	—	} ν N-H
3320sh	3380w	3310s	3370w	3335w	—	—	—	
3280w	—	—	3280w	3200w	—	3300mbr	3300mbr	} ν N-H
3240w	3240sh	3230w	3240sh	3260w	3240sh	—	—	
2930s	2930m	2960s	2980s	2970s	2980m	2960w	2960w	2(δ NH ₂)
2870m	2890w	2840w	2980w	2890m	2880m	—	—	ν_{as} (C-H)
—	1650sh	1650s	1630sh	—	1650w	1680w	1690sh	ν_s (C-H)
—	1620w	1620w	1620s	1625w	1630sh	1630m	1620w	ν C-O
1585s	1605w	1585s	1600w	1600s	1610s	1620s	1580w	δ NH ₂
—	1515s	150Cs	1570s	1505vw	1570s	1515sh	1515w	ν_s (C-N) + ν_s (N-H)
1450w	1465w	1470w	—	1460s	1460s	1455m	1455w	CH ₂ and CH ₃ asym. deform.
1270m	1265s	1280s	1250s	1275s	1265s	1265w	—	ν_s (C-N)
—	1205m	1215s	—	1200m	1200s	1200w	1200w	} CH ₂ rock + ν_{as} C-C-C
1140w	1155w	1170s	1175w	1160m	—	1145w	1145w	
1080vs	1035w	1035w	1030w	—	—	—	—	} C-NH ₂
—	1025s	—	—	—	—	—	—	
1015w	1010w	1000w	1015w	1020s	1020s	1020m	1015w	} (C-N) + ν (N-H)
—	770vw	785s	780s	—	770s	760w	—	
425m	430m	450m	435m	445w	420s	445s	440w	ν (N-N)

Table 2 indicates all mixed ligand complex show four bands in the range 1690-1500 cm⁻¹. The ν C=C, ν C=N, ν (NH₂) and ν C=O (β -keto compound) stretches are clearly observed in all the complexes. The systematic presence of C=C, C=N and C=O stretches is a necessary condition for the mixed ligand formulation¹¹. However, it is difficult to assign all band in the region 1690-1500 cm⁻¹, only tentative assignment of such ligand system can be given.

Direct evidence for M-O bonding could only be observed at about 440 cm⁻¹ but all the M-O frequencies could not be obtained as M-O falls below the range of the instrument used.

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Synthesis and Spectral Studies of Lanthanide Complexes with Fluoro β -diketones

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LANTHANIDE β -diketonates have been found to have wide applications as pseudocontact nmr shift reagents¹⁻³. Some of these chelates have been used for the chromatographic separation of lanthanides⁴⁻⁵. The paper describes the synthesis of anhydrous chelates of lanthanides with trifluoro, hexafluoro acetyl-acetone, benzoyl trifluoroacetone and pentafluoro benzoyl acetone and characterization of these by magnetic and spectral studies.

Experimental

Diaquo tris chelates of lanthanides with these